

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP2 – Real-World Testing of Digital Cognitive Assessments

D2.1 Core protocol for digital cognitive assessment

Lead contributor	Sikkes, S.A.M. , Flier, W.M. van der (7 – VUmc)
Other contributors	Roos Jutten, VUmc (7), Tim McLeaod, Ties Hoomans, DAC (8), Miia Kivipelto, Rosita Tengzelius RS (1), Michael Scholl, UGOT (4), Sebastian Palmqvist, Rik Ossenkoppele LU (5), Alina Solomon, UEF (6), Marc Suarez, Gonzalo Sánchez Benavides, Andreea Rădoi, Iva Knezevic BBRC (9), Geraint Price, IMPERIAL (11), Patrizia Meccoci, UNIPG (15), Jyrki Lotjonen, Combinostics (19), David Berron, Neotiv (24), Nick Taplikis, CCL (21),
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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset - Sweden (**The Coordinator**)

KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society - Sweden

FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute - Sweden

UGOT: Goteborgs Universitet - Sweden

ULUND: Lunds Universitet - Sweden

UEF: Itä-Suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland - Finland

VUMC: Stichting VUmc - The Netherlands

UM: Universiteit Maastricht - The Netherlands

BBRC: Fundació Barcelonabeta Brain Research Center - Spain

SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L - Spain

AE: Alzheimer Europe - Luxembourg

ADI: Alzheimer’s Disease International – United States

UNIPG: Università Degli Studi di Perugia - Italy

GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)

DAC: Davos Alzheimer’s Collaborative - Switzerland

COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy - Finland

Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV - Belgium

SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development - France

C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States

neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH - Germany

CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom

ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom

ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine - United Kingdom

NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence- United Kingdom

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties’ obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This **Deliverable (D2.1)** provides the core protocol for AD-RIDDLE **WP2 on Digital Cognitive Assessments**. The goal of AD-RIDDLE WP2 is to conduct real-world testing of digital cognitive biomarkers to improve early AD detection and prediction of cognitive decline and dementia. This deliverable describes the development of a **Core Protocol** for Digital Cognitive Assessments (DCAs) for implementation in the Real-World Testing, aligned with Blood-based Biomarker (BBM) testing in WP3 and implementation in WP5. The Core Protocol includes a library of cognitive digital tools available for use at each of the sites (T2.1), provides a synopsis for the sub-study concerning the pilot stage of real-world testing (T2.2), and lays out the framework for the large-scale studies testing digital cognitive biomarkers in real-world settings (T.2.3). The Core Protocol including sub-studies has been developed collaboratively with relevant site leads and industry in-kind contributing partners. It lays the foundation for successful execution of WP2 across each of the sites.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer’s disease (AD) requires innovative approaches for early detection and prevention. Compared with standard paper-and-pencil testing, digital cognitive assessment (DCA) tools have great potential due to their higher sensitivity to early disease and better ecological validity. Additionally, by removing the need for individuals to travel for their cognitive assessment(s), sensitive, specific, and valuable cognitive measures could be captured on a large scale with ease, while offering greater cost-efficiencies, accessibility, and data aggregation.

The overall goal of AD-RIDDLE Work Package 2 is to conduct real-world testing of validated and novel/exploratory DCAs to improve early AD detection and prediction of cognitive decline and dementia. Crucial for successful real-life testing is optimal implementation of digital tools in daily practice. Despite rapid useful developments in AI, remote testing and digital tools, there is a gap when considering validation and implementation in memory-clinics and community-based settings. Stakeholders are overall highly positive towards use of digital tools, yet also point out that there are many hurdles to actually integrate and use digital tools in routine care practices. Thus, a careful selection of DCAs as well as pilot testing these selected tools in a real-world setting is needed to prepare for larger scale testing and moving towards sustainable implementation.

We aim to achieve this by addressing the following key objectives:

- **Task 2.1:** Prepare the real-world testing i.e., optimize validated DCAs with input from relevant stakeholders; provide clinical sites with a library of operational and culturally relevant digital tools;
- **Task 2.2.** Conduct a pilot study to determine feasibility and usability of digital biomarkers;
- **Task 2.3:** Conduct a large-scale study testing DCAs (in combination with blood-based biomarkers) in real-world settings across the patient journey;
- **Task 2.4:** Perform data analyses using mixed methods, integrating quantitative and qualitative data.

The current report describes the Core Protocol (D2.1) and the start of preparing harmonized real-world testing of DCAs in multiple different sites/countries, aligned with BBMs testing in WP3. Taking the Core Protocol as a starting point, each site will develop site-specific sub-study protocols. Sub-studies for the pilot stage of real-world testing (T2.2) will be prepared first, while sub-studies for the large-scale study (T2.3) will be developed in a later stage and only a broad outline is provided here.

2. PREPARING REAL WORLD TESTING BY PROVIDING A LIBRARY OF DIGITAL COGNITIVE ASSESSMENTS

The selection of DCAs for the Core Protocol was performed by leveraging the expertise of AD-RIDDLE Consortium Participants (VUmc, DAC, RS, UGOT, LU, UEF, BBRC, IMPERIAL, UNIPG, COMBINOSTICS, neotiv GmbH, CCL, G) and with input from relevant stakeholders. As a first criterion, we assessed digital cognitive tools available for real world testing and use. In addition, we assessed the tools (i) from the perspective healthcare professionals (HCPs) and that of broader healthcare systems (HCSs) to identify barriers and

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facilitators for implementation; and (ii) from patient perspectives (relevance as well as inclusiveness for diverse populations, feasibility, and usability).

2.1. HCP/HCS perspectives

Previous work has shown that most clinicians, patients, and care partners are supportive of the use of computer tools in memory clinics, including tools for web-based cognitive testing. Facilitating factors are mainly practical (tools should be user-friendly) and technical (connection with electronic patient files) and that tools should increase diagnostic accuracy. Identified barriers mainly focus on doubts regarding reliability and validity, preservation of clinical autonomy, and fear of losing important clinical information (Van Gils et al. JMIR 2021).

2.2. Patient perspectives

We assessed barriers and facilitators for using DCAs using focus groups with individuals at risk for Alzheimer’s disease (Van der Landen et al, submitted). Participants recognized the added value of digital cognitive assessments. Facilitators and barriers were identified concerning test motivation, digital test suitability, and digital test characteristics. Early disease recognition and user-friendliness were important facilitators, whereas fear of dementia, lack of personal contact, and digital illiteracy could hinder the use.

2.3 Library of DCA’s

Based on implementation-readiness, the following DCA’s have been identified for the Core Protocol: cCog; Amsterdam IADL Questionnaire; Neotiv; CANTAB; and BioCog. **Table 1** provides an overview of each tool, the organization that developed them, device types needed to use the DCA and a brief description of duration, type of tests, some high-level information on test characteristics, and a reference for in depth description.

Table 1. Library of digital cognitive assessments available for use in AD-RIDDLE.			
Tool	AD-RIDDLE Partner	Device Type(s)	Brief Description
cCog	Combinostics	Tablet/Computer	20-mins. self-administered battery on memory, speed, attention, visuospatial, and executive functioning. Correlates with traditional paper-and-pencil test and differentiates between healthy controls, MCI and dementia, and between AD and different types of dementia. [1,2]
Amsterdam IADL Questionnaire	Amsterdam UMC	Tablet/Computer	10-min questionnaire completed by a proxy of the patient (e.g., spouse). Targets functional impairment in cognitively complex daily activities, e.g., handling finances, using everyday technology. Extensively validated for use in (preclinical) AD and related disorders (diagnostic

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			use, content and construct validity, longitudinal validity, and clinical meaningfulness). [3,4]
Neotiv	Neotiv	Tablet/Smartphone	Suite of novel cognitive tests that are suitable for the detection of early preclinical cognitive impairment due to their relationship to specific brain regions. Test included: mnemonic discrimination task-objects and scenes, object-in-room recall and complex scene recognition. [5,6]
CANTAB	Cambridge Cognition	Computer/Tablet/ Smartphone	The Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB) includes highly sensitive, precise and objective measures of cognitive function, correlated to neural networks. CANTAB tests have demonstrated sensitivity to detecting changes in neuropsychological performance and include tests of working memory, learning and executive function; visual, verbal and episodic memory; attention, information processing and reaction time; social and emotion recognition, decision making and response control. [7,8]
BioCog	Lunds Universitet	Tablet	Self-administered cognitive assessment battery. It includes a wordlist test with immediate and delayed recall, a modified Symbol Digit Modalities Test, orientation to time, a story-picture learning test, a reaction time test, Trail Making Tests A and B, and a paired associates test. The test battery is divided into two parts: the first part takes approximately 10 minutes to complete, and the second part takes an additional 15 minutes, totaling 25 minutes.

3. PILOT TESTING DIGITAL COGNITIVE ASSESSMENTS

During a live WP2 meeting that took place at the Alzheimer’s Association International Conference (AAIC) in Philadelphia July 2024, and during ensuing monthly online WP2 meetings, the synopsis for task 2.2 Pilot Testing Digital Cognitive Assessments has been developed with consortium partners. Based on this core protocol, each site develops a sub-study protocol for the pilot stage, including site-specific details (e.g., recruitment sources and procedures, relevant clinical settings, digital tools).

3.1. Objective

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The objective of the pilot study on DCA's is to determine feasibility and usability of the different DCAs in a memory clinic setting. In addition, we aim to harmonize DCA's by correlating their results to paper-and-pencil tests for future real-world testing. Cross-country comparisons will be conducted to identify best practices and learnings.

3.2. Study Design

The DCA Pilot Study design entails a cross-sectional comparison of digital cognitive assessments, and we plan a study population of N=150 (n=50 SCD, n=50 MCI and n=50 dementia), covering the entire disease spectrum. Participants will undergo a baseline paper-and-pencil cognitive assessment in the clinic, followed by remote digital cognitive assessments at home (in random order), with 1-week intervals to avoid test interference.

All clinical sites plan to participate in the Pilot Study (we aim for a minimum of 6 sites). Table 2 provides an overview of sites, their source cohort, target population/ clinical context.

Site	Setting	Target population
BBRC	Beta-AARC study cohort	Mostly SCD / community based
Lund	BioFinder	SCD, MCI & dementia
Gothenburg	REAL-AD study and memory clinic	CN, MCI & dementia/general population
Imperial	CANTAB	General population
Stockholm	Memory clinic	SCD, MCI & dementia
Kuopio	Memory clinic	SCD and MCI
Perugia	Memory clinic	SCD, MCI and dementia
Amsterdam UMC	Amsterdam Dementia Cohort	SCD, MCI and dementia

3.3. Study Population

We will include memory-clinic patients over 40 years old with subjective cognitive decline (SCD), a diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or (mild) Alzheimer's disease (AD) dementia. In addition, cognitively normal individuals aged 40 and older from the general population may also participate. Each site aims to enroll 20 to 30 participants (e.g., n=10 SCD, n=10 MCI and n=10 AD at one site, but distribution may differ according to local circumstances), aiming to reach a total of $\geq n=150$.

Inclusion criteria

- 40 years or older;
- Access to and experience with a touchscreen-based device;
- Willing and able to provide informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

- (Other) neurological and/or psychiatric disorders;
- Visual or auditive impairments that hamper use of DCAs.

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3.4. Study Parameters

Study parameters for each individual DCA are identified in collaboration with the respective AD-RIDDLE partners (Combinostics, Amsterdam UMC, CANTAB, Neotiv, Lund).

Total scores from paper-and-pencil cognitive tests (i.e., MMSE or MOCA, RBANSS, and the (modified) PACC) will be derived according to standardized procedures for each test.

3.5. Study Endpoints

- Feasibility: Aspect of onboarding (phone calls, etc.). Quality characteristics
- Usability: Usability questionnaire (exact questionnaire TBD): USE/SUS
- Concordance: associations between digital cognitive assessments and standard paper-and-pencil cognitive tests
- Compare DCA scores across clinical groups.

3.6. Statistical Analysis

- Descriptive statistics (e.g., mean, standard deviation, median) for each DCA
- Correlations between DCAs and traditional cognitive tests (Pearson's correlations)
- Prepare for harmonization/ pooled analysis future studies, e.g., determine associations between DCAs + bridging algorithms.

4. LARGE SCALE EVALUATION OF DIGITAL COGNITIVE ASSESSMENTS IN REAL-WORLD SETTINGS

Taking the learnings of the pilot study into account, including diversity of contexts of use, different study populations, heterogeneity in characteristics of the different DCA's, we continue large scale testing of the application of DCA's in real world patient journeys (T2.3). Details of the large-scale study protocol will be further delineated a later stage, with input from WP3 and based on results from the pilot study. As such, only a broad outline is provided here.

4.1. Objective

The objective is to conduct a large-scale study testing digital cognitive assessments in real-world settings across the patient journey at several sites in 6 European countries (Sweden, Finland, Netherlands, Spain, Italy, UK). We aim to leverage on several large-scale studies going on at specific sites.

Site	Setting	DCA
BBRC	Alfa, Alfa+ cohorts (community) and BETA-AARC cohort (similar to memory clinic)	cCOG, A-IADL-Q
Lund	BioFinder (memory clinic)	BioCog, A-IADL-Q
Gothenburg	REAL-AD (community)	Neotiv
Imperial	(community)	CANTAB

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Stockholm	Memory clinic	cCOG, A-IADL-Q
Kuopio	Memory clinic	cCOG, A-IADL-Q
Perugia	Memory clinic	cCOG, A-IADL-Q
Amsterdam UMC	ADC cohort (memory clinic); ABOARD-cohort (community)	cCOG, A-IADL-Q

4.2. Study Design and Population

Large scale testing will entail a longitudinal study with a two-year follow-up period. Depending on local possibilities, participants will include a mix of memory clinic-based patients and community-based individuals. Protocols are in place at Lund, Gothenburg, and Imperial. We will draft a core protocol for Stockholm, BBRC, Perugia and Amsterdam. Each site will recruit a minimum of 250 participants, resulting in a total sample size of at least 2000 ($n \geq 2000$). Inclusion and exclusion criteria are largely similar to those used in the pilot study (see above). The study is aligned with WP3 (BBM). During the conduct of the large scale study, interviews and focus groups may be conducted with relevant stakeholders to assess feasibility and foster future implementation.

4.3. Study Endpoints

- Primary outcomes: cognitive change over time on the DCAs, progression to MCI or dementia, seeking help for cognitive problems.
- Secondary outcome: Concordance with (change in) paper-and-pencil cognitive tests, with (change in) BBM or reference standard biomarkers (CSF/ PET)
- Exploratory: diagnostic algorithm based on DCA or combination of DCA with BBM to improve work-up and patient flow.

4.4. Statistical Analysis

- Based on results of pilot study, data are harmonized across sites for pooled analysis.
- Linear mixed models to study change over time and associations with paper-and-pencil tests and BBM
- Cox proportional hazards models to determine associations with clinical progression and seeking help.

5. INTEGRATING QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE DATA

Digital biomarkers generate high-dimensional data files from different platforms and systems. Integrative analyses, including qualitative components, are essential to study — and potentially promote — their implementation of in real-world practice. We will use a broad mixed methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative data collected in T2.2 and 2.3. In collaboration with WP3 and WP4, we will determine the optimal funneling approach to accommodate a stepwise early diagnostic framework. In addition, we will translate qualitative data into guidelines for optimal implementation of digital cognitive assessments, leveraging mixed methods and the Early Detection Toolkit of Consortium partner DAC, in collaboration with WP5.

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6. DISCUSSION

WP2 conducts monthly online meetings, where main aspects of the Pilot Study protocol and validation Study protocol (in- and exclusion criteria; study design; endpoints) are reviewed and discussed amongst project partners. Partners representing PMO, WP3 (BBMs) and WP5 (implementation) are invited to ensure optimal exchange between work packages.

The current deliverable provides a core protocol for the sub-studies to be conducted within WP2 on digital cognitive assessments (DCA). Based on discussions amongst consortium partners, input from relevant stakeholders as well as implementation-readiness, five DCAs have been identified for further pilot testing (Task 2.1): cCog; Amsterdam IADL Questionnaire; Neotiv; CANTAB; BioCog. The core protocol describes the synopsis for the Pilot Study (Task 2.2), which will entail a cross-sectional comparison of DCAs and extant approaches (in-clinic cognitive testing) in $\geq N=150$ participants ($n=50$ SCD, $n=50$ MCI and $n=50$ dementia) recruited from all AD-RIDDLE clinical sites. Based on the core-protocol, sites will develop site-specific protocols.

This core protocol also outlines the framework for the large-scale validation studies. The framework will be further developed into a concise synopsis, after which local sub-protocols are made.

Of note, preparations for core protocol have taken a bit a longer than anticipated. We expect to have IRB approval in most sites by M18 – after which data collection probably takes a further 12 months. Data collection for the large-scale validation can start taking place in parallel, hence we do not expect large deviations from timelines.

7. CONCLUSION

This deliverable provides the core protocol for WP2 on DCAs. It describes a library of DCAs available for the project partners, the synopsis of the pilot study evaluating the use of DCAs, and the groundwork for the large-scale study testing digital cognitive biomarkers. Ultimately, validated and easily accessible DCAs and blood-based biomarkers will enable patients with preclinical or prodromal Alzheimer's disease to receive a timely diagnosis and be directed towards personalized therapies to prevent or delay dementia onset.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1: References of selected Digital Cognitive Assessments

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